
Effects of scaling when modeling with KNN

A Data Management Plan created using dmponline

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Template: DCC Template

Project abstract:

Learning project to demonstrate an effect of scaling numerical feature on resulting model when using KNN. Using two datasets and building two KNN models for each, where one is with scaling of numerical features and other without. This project is used for educational purposes to demonstrate the importance of scaling when using KNN.

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Data Collection

What data will you collect or create?

The project focuses on modeling with already publicly available datasets, we will only collect and create the predictions for the testing data set produced by the algorithms after pre processing and cleaning.

Data created as csv with following naming convention:

- `<data_set>_scale_experiment.csv`
- `<data_set>_no_scale_experiment.csv`

Where the scale and no scale variants are with and without scaling of numerical features. I expect the data size of each csv to be in range of single digit MB.

It will be shared in CSV format with index and target variable prediction with appropriate headers. CSV is a commonly used format also suitable for long term storage.

Visual data created of statistics for original datasets will be shared as .png format.

How will the data be collected or created?

Data will be created using the code snippet in python to create train/test split of the original data, and predicting values for the testing set. For reproducibility the random seed (42) and size of the split will be fixed (1/3). For scaling we will use StandardScaler from scikit-learn.

Original raw data are taken from:

- [bike sharing](#)
- [auto mpg](#)

Prediction data will be only created after the initial phase of the project which will find all the inconsistencies in the algorithm.

Prediction datasets will be structured in folder **predictions** and for each dataset there will be dedicated folder, each of the folders will contain two .csv files.

Data created as csv will be in following format:

- `<data_set>_scale_experiment.csv`
- `<data_set>_no_scale_experiment.csv`

Where the scale and no scale variants are with and without scaling of numerical features. And `<data_set>` is either `auto_mpg` or `bike_sharing`.

Images created will be placed in folder **visualizations**, where all images will be placed. Following naming convention will be used:

- `<data_set>_<variable displayed>_dist.png`

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

Data will be paired with a markdown document (README.md) specifying the source of the original data, and list of columns considered for predictions. Short description will be added to computed features, so it's clear what they represent also in the future. Since we are using publicly available data for our analysis and prediction, these information can be also looked for.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage any ethical issues?

Raw data are anonymous and public already. Transforming those data and creating prediction for same domain has very limited ethical issues, which we don't really have to consider.

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

I will not claim ownership of the data created as they will be re-shared under public licence as the original raw data. Data sharing will be immediate after publishing the project.

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

Data we create are very small (in range of MB) and will be backed up in GitHub repository, which is a reliable storage for many projects. Should anything change with GitHub in future, the choice will be reevaluated.

I will be responsible for the back up and restoring of these data if anything unfortunate would happen. Additionally the original data are published in digital data repository from which the data can be always recreated using the published source code.

How will you manage access and security?

Data used are public and the whole code source for experiment and creation of them will be published along the data. There are no concerns about security of the data as I will be working with already publicly available resources.

Access and right to the repository on GitHub will remain in my possession, where collaborators can follow the standard process of Pull Request for requesting change in the project.

Selection and Preservation

Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

Data created are to be kept until needed by the learning need of students at TU Wien. There are not data that needs to be destroyed. Should such need emerge in future, we will comply with the regulatory instructions (privacy leaks, data linkage).

All four csv are to be retained and published, additionally also the visualizations are to be shared, but it's not critical they are retained for as long as the prediction datasets.

Additional sharing of the new data will be discussed with project creator (Dusan Trnka) and could be initiated via public Pull Request to the repository.

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

Data will be published on public GitHub repository, which is also the long term preservation plan for the data.

There are currently no cost of having data on GitHub, should this change we will reevaluate the possibilities and possibly move the data to minimalism the cost associated with it.

Data Sharing

How will you share the data?

I will share the DMP on Zenodo platform with a publication status and also the whole experiment is stored in a [GitHub](#) open repository. Data will be available from 19.4.2021. Anyone can access the repository so no approval process is required.

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

No, there are no restriction on sharing this data. It will be shared immediately after the project is published, and under public use licence.

Responsibilities and Resources**Who will be responsible for data management?**

I, Dusan Trnka will be the sole responsible for data management.

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

No, only free software and ML libraries will be used. Along with publicly available datasets of auto_mpg and bike_sharing.